

Two cases concerning respectively access to research materials and prison leave referred to the Grand Chamber

Two cases have been referred to the Grand Chamber of the European Court of Human Rights – ***Gillberg v. Sweden***, which concerns a professor's criminal conviction for refusing to comply with a court decision granting access to his research to other researchers, and ***Boulois v. Luxembourg***, which concerns the refusal of several requests for temporary leave of absence ("prison leave") lodged by a detainee and in particular the proceedings by which he complained about these refusals.

On 11 April 2011, the Court decided to refer these two cases to the Grand Chamber and to reject requests to refer 52 other cases/groups of cases¹.

Referrals accepted

[Gillberg v. Sweden \(application no. 41723/06\)](#)

The applicant, Christopher Gillberg, is a Swedish national who was born in 1950. He is a well-known professor and former Head of Department of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry at the University of Gothenburg (Sweden) where he carried out research on hyperactivity and attention-deficit disorders. He complained about his criminal conviction in 2006 for refusing to comply with a court decision granting access to his research material for a sociologist and a paediatrician. The applicant refused as he had allegedly promised absolute confidentiality to the families of the children who took part in his research. He was given a suspended sentence and a fine of 750 Swedish kronor (approximately 4,000 Euros (EUR)).

In its [judgment](#) of 2 November 2010, the Chamber held, by five votes to two that there had been no violation of Article 8 (right to respect for private and family life) of the European Convention on Human Rights, and, unanimously, that there had been no violation of Article 10 (freedom of expression) of the Convention.

That case was referred to the Grand Chamber at the applicant's request.

[Boulois v. Luxembourg \(no. 37575/04\)](#)

The applicant, Thomas Boulois, is a French national who was born in 1972 and is currently being held under a semi-custodial regime in Givenich Prison (Luxembourg), having been sentenced to 15 years' imprisonment for assault occasioning actual bodily harm, rape and false imprisonment accompanied by acts of torture. Between 2003 and 2006 he submitted several requests for temporary leave of absence ("prison leave"), stating, in particular, that he wished to carry out administrative tasks and to take courses to gain qualifications. All his requests were refused. He complained that the

¹ Under Article 43 of the European Convention on Human Rights, within three months from the date of a Chamber judgment, any party to the case may, in exceptional cases, request that the case be referred to the 17-member Grand Chamber of the Court. In that event, a panel of five judges considers whether the case raises a serious question affecting the interpretation or application of the Convention or its protocols, or a serious issue of general importance, in which case the Grand Chamber will deliver a final judgment. If no such question or issue arises, the panel will reject the request, at which point the judgment becomes final. Otherwise Chamber judgments become final on the expiry of the three-month period or earlier if the parties declare that they do not intend to make a request to refer.

proceedings had not been fair and that he had been denied access to a court in respect of the decisions refusing his requests for prison leave.

In its [judgment](#) of 14 December 2010, the Chamber held, by four votes to three that there had been a violation of Article 6 § 1.

That case was referred to the Grand Chamber at the Government's request.

Requests for referral rejected

Judgments in the following cases are now final²:

Vrioni and Others v. Albania (nos. 35720/04 and 42832/06), judgment of 7 December 2010;

Kugler v. Austria (n° 65631/01), judgment of 14 October 2010;

von Pezold v. Austria (no. 5339/07), judgment of 28 October 2010;

Muradverdiyev v. Azerbaijan (no. 16966/06), judgment of 9 December 2010;

Georgi Atanasov v. Bulgaria (no. 5359/04), judgment of 7 October 2010;

Ivan Atanasov v. Bulgaria (no. 12853/03), judgment of 2 December 2010;

Tarkoiev and Others v. Estonia (nos. 14480/08 and 47916/08), judgment of 4 November 2010;

Dervaux v. France (no. 40975/07), judgment of 4 November 2010;

Grosskopf v. Germany (no. 24478/03), judgment of 21 October 2010;

Anonymos Touristiki Etairia Xenodocheia Kritis v. Greece (no. 35332/05), judgment (just satisfaction) of 2 December 2010;

Theodoraki and Others v. Greece (no. 9368/06), judgment (just satisfaction) of 2 December 2010;

Gautieri and Others v. Italy (no. 68610/01), judgment of 14 December 2010;

I. D. v. Moldova (no. 47203/06), judgment of 30 November 2010;

Aune v. Norway (no. 52502/07), judgment of 28 October 2010;

Kristina Misiak and Jan Misiak v. Poland (no. 31193/04), judgment of 9 November 2010;

Piotr Nowak v. Poland (no. 7337/05), judgment of 7 December 2010;

Witek v. Poland (no. 13453/07), judgment of 21 December 2010;

Cernescu and Manolache v. Romania (no. 28607/04), judgment of 30 November 2010;

² Under Article 44 § 2 (c) of the European Convention on Human Rights, the judgment of a Chamber becomes final when the panel of the Grand Chamber rejects the request to refer under Article 43.

Marcu v. Romania (no. 43079/02), judgment of 26 October 2010;

Raban v. Romania (no. 25437/08), judgment of 26 October 2010;

S. V. Apron Dynamics SRL Baia Mare v. Romania (no. 21199/03), judgment of 2 November 2010;

Abuyeva and Others v. Russia (no. 27065/05), judgment of 2 December 2010;

Aleksandr Leonidovich Ivanov v. Russia (no. 33929/03), judgment of 23 September 2010;

[Alekseyev v. Russia](#) (nos. 4916/07, 25924/08 and 14599/09), judgment of 21 October 2010;

Dzhabrailova and Dzhabrailova v. Russia (no. 15563/06), judgment of 2 December 2010;

Gaforov v. Russia (no. 25404/09), judgment of 21 October 2010;

Petr Korolev v. Russia (no. 38112/04), judgment of 21 October 2010;

Roman Karasev v. Russia (no. 30251/03), judgment of 25 November 2010;

Rudakov v. Russia (no. 43239/04), judgment of 28 October 2010;

Sasita Israilova and Others v. Russia (no. 35079/04), judgment of 28 October 2010;

Sultanov v. Russia (no. 15303/09), judgment of 4 November 2010;

Svetlana Kazmina v. Russia (no. 8609/04), judgment of 2 December 2010;

Yuriy Lobanov v. Russia (no. 15578/03), judgment of 2 December 2010;

P.V. v. Spain (no. 35159/09), judgment of 30 November 2010;

Vaquero Hernández and Others v. Spain (nos. 1883/03, 2723/03 and 4058/03), judgment of 2 November 2010;

Sirotnák v. Slovakia (no. 30633/06), judgment of 21 December 2010;

Erbey v. Turkey (no. 29188/02), judgment of 26 October 2010;

Hüseyin AK and Others v. Turkey (nos. 15523/04 and 15891/04), judgment of 7 December 2010;

Liman-Iş Sendikası v. Turkey (nos. 29608/05, 36239/05 and 36247/05), judgment of 12 October 2010;

Lordos and Others v. Turkey (no. 15973/90), judgment of 2 November 2010;

Mehmet Özcan and Others v. Turkey (nos. 20613/09, 20636/09, 4018/07, 4019/07, 4172/07, 23562/07, 36595/07, 54508/07, 54520/07, 2539/08, 16353/08, 34350/08, 34379/08, 35269/08, 37798/08, 37818/08, 56422/08, 20437/09, 20440/09, 20453/09, 20460/09, 20568/09, 20604/09 and 20608/09), judgment of 26 October 2010;

Sadik Bilgin v. Turkey (no. 4038/06), judgment of 23 November 2010;

Şeyhmus Uğur and Others v. Turkey (nos. 36541/07, 15637/08, 1968/07, 3608/07, 14474/07, 35240/07, 35252/07, 36503/07, 36505/07, 36509/07, 36544/07, 36556/07, 36563/07, 36571/07, 36573/07, 36582/07, 36586/07, 36593/07, 34229/08, 36489/08, 36492/08, 36493/08, 37232/08 and 37233/08), judgment of 19 October 2010;

Suna v. Turkey (no. 1058/06), judgment of 9 November 2010;

Vardar v. Turkey (no. 35150/06), judgment of 26 October 2010;

Vrahimi v. Turkey (no. 16078/90), **Strati v. Turkey** (no. 16082/90), **Christodoulidou v. Turkey** (no. 16085/90), **Olymbiou v. Turkey** (no. 16091/90), **Andreou Papi v. Turkey** (no. 16094/90), **Saveriades v. Turkey** (no. 16190/90), **Diogeneous and Tseriotis v. Turkey** (no. 16259/90), **Zavou and Others v. Turkey** (no. 16654/90), **Loizou and Others v. Turkey** (no. 16682/90), **Epiphaniou and Others v. Turkey** (no. 19900/92), **Josephides v. Turkey** (no. 21887/93), **Ramon v. Turkey** (no. 29092/95), **Hapeshis and Hapeshi-Michaelidou v. Turkey** (no. 35214/97), **Hadjiprocopiou and Others v. Turkey** (no. 37395/97), **Hapeshis and Others v. Turkey** (no. 38179/97), **Hadjithomas and Others v. Turkey** (no. 39970/98), **Iordanis Iordanou v. Turkey** (no. 43685/98), **Rock Ruby Hotels Ltd. v. Turkey** (no. 46159/99), **Skyropiia Yialias Ltd. v. Turkey** (no. 47884/99), judgments (just satisfaction) of 26 October 2010;

Yusuf Karataş v. Turkey (no. 31953/05), judgment of 26 October 2010;

Krivova v. Ukraine (no. 25732/05), judgment of 9 November 2010;

Pokhalchuk v. Ukraine (no. 7193/02), judgment of 7 October 2010;

Zhuk v. Ukraine (no. 45783/05), judgment of 21 October 2010;

[Greens and M.T. v. United Kingdom](#) (nos. 60041/08 and 60054/08), judgment of 23 November 2010;

Seal v. United Kingdom (no. 50330/07), judgment of 7 December 2010.

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The European Court of Human Rights was set up in Strasbourg by the Council of Europe Member States in 1959 to deal with alleged violations of the 1950 European Convention on Human Rights.